

CLIMATE TIPPING POINTS

RISKS AND IMPACTS

10 key takeaways

Based on the presentations and discussions at the “Climate Tipping Points: Risks and Impacts” event, which took place on 2 June 2026, hosted by the TipESM project and the National Center for Climate Research (DMI). Presenters: Shuting Yang (DMI), Torben Koenigk (SMHI), Didier Swingedouw (CNRS, University of Bordeaux), Andrew Hartley (UK Met Office). Moderator: Adrian Lema (DMI)

1. A tipping point is a critical threshold, where a small, gradual change triggers a strong, often irreversible shift in a system's state. Examples of systems that can experience a tipping point include the Greenland and West Antarctic Ice Sheets, with risk of large melting, the Atlantic Meridional Ocean Circulation (AMOC), with risk of a very substantial weakening, and the Boreal and Amazon forests, with risk of large-scale dieback. If these systems pass their tipping points, the resulting changes may be difficult or impossible to reverse on human timescales.
2. The risk of abrupt and irreversible changes to the Earth's climate due to crossing a tipping point increases with higher global warming levels.¹ In essence, as the planet warms, the likelihood of crossing tipping points increases.
3. The Amazon rainforest is often called the “lungs of the Earth”, because it absorbs a large amount of CO₂. Terrestrial ecosystems currently absorb roughly one third of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions, making land a major global carbon sink.² Increasing droughts linked to global warming could potentially cause the Amazon to abruptly transition to a savannah-like ecosystem with enormous consequences for the global climate, ecosystems, biodiversity, indigenous communities, and food and water security across South America.
4. The Greenland ice sheet tipping point refers to the threshold, where the ice sheet keeps shrinking due to self-reinforcing processes, even if the climate would cool again. If global mean temperature would stabilise at a higher level (e.g., 1.5 degrees or higher), the ice sheet will continue to lose ice for centuries or millenia. If all of the Greenland ice sheet were to melt, it could contribute up to 7 meters of global sea level rise³ – but even partial melting leads to substantial sea level rise, increasing coastal flooding and threatening infrastructure and ecosystems.
5. In general, rising temperatures linked to anthropogenic emissions of CO₂ are the common reason for the triggering of climate tipping points. For example, the Greenland Ice Sheet and Antarctic Ice Sheet are melting due to rising temperatures (both in the atmosphere and in the ocean). Meanwhile, the melting ice increases freshwater influx into the Atlantic ocean, contributing to the weakening of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC).

Fig. 1. Selected systems that can experience a tipping point, which would result in large changes difficult or impossible to reverse on human timescales. Source: TIPMIP, 2026.

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6. The interactions between tipping points don't end there - researchers are investigating the so-called "tipping points cascades", where some tipping points result in processes that impact other tipping points. Research shows that tipping point cascades are predominantly initiated by the polar ice sheets melting, and mediated by the AMOC⁴.

Weakening of the AMOC leads to a slowdown in ocean heat circulation, resulting in heat accumulation in the Southern Ocean and reduced warming in the North Atlantic. This has multiple impacts, including disruptions to monsoon systems (particularly over West Africa), destabilisation of the West Antarctic Ice Sheet, and increased drought risk in the northern Amazon rainforest.

Tipping points may also contribute to stabilising other tipping elements. For example the cooler temperatures in the north caused by an AMOC weakening or collapse, may slow down Greenland Ice Sheet melt.

Fig. 2. The AMOC redistributes heat across the North Atlantic Ocean, warming northwest Europe. Surface flows (red) move heat north before cooling, sinking, and returning south along the sea floor (blue). This process is powered by deep-water formation, which takes place in the North Atlantic. Climate change could slow this process, causing sharp cooldown in Europe. Source: Voosen, 2026.

7. Substantial AMOC weakening by itself can have broad-reaching consequences, not only on other elements of the climate system but also on ecosystems, industries and livelihoods. The weather patterns would change significantly, bringing lower average temperatures and much lower rainfall to large parts of Europe.

This would have direct effects on agriculture and food production in the region. The sea level would also increase substantially, threatening the coastal communities.

8. The sub-polar gyre is part of the larger AMOC located south of Greenland and Iceland, from the Canadian east coast to the west coast of the United Kingdom. It plays a crucial role in regulating regional climate due its ability to remain relatively warm in winter through convection processes . This convective activity also supports marine ecosystems by supporting plankton growth, feeding fish populations, and sustaining fisheries important to local economies. The sub-polar gyre is often overlooked in the discussion on tipping points, although research indicates there is a risk of its abrupt cooling in just about 10 years and occurring within this century⁵.

9. Reducing greenhouse gas emissions is essential to limit global warming and minimise the risks of extreme climate events and crossing climate tipping points. Once a tipping point is crossed, the resulting changes may be irreversible on human timescales, meaning that emissions reductions alone may no longer be sufficient to prevent their consequences. Despite this risk, climate adaptation plans and climate risk management strategies often do not adequately account for the possibility of crossing tipping points. This underscores the need for rapid and sustained emissions reductions to lower the likelihood of crossing critical thresholds and triggering irreversible changes in the Earth system.

10. All global tipping points are of concern: it is difficult to assess which one is the most "urgent" or matters most. They are interconnected, and they have different - but similarly threatening - consequences.

References:

¹ IPCC, 2021. *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157896>

² Friedlingstein, P. et al., 2023. *Global Carbon Budget 2023*. Earth Syst. Sci. Data. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-15-5301-2023>

³ Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), n.d. *Ice sheets - climate indicators*. ECMWF. Available at: <https://climate.copernicus.eu/climate-indicators/ice-sheets>

⁴ Wunderling, N. et al., 2021. *Interacting tipping elements increase risk of climate domino effects under global warming*. Earth Syst. Dynam, 12(2). <https://doi.org/10.5194/esd-12-601-2021>

⁵ Armstrong McKay, D.I. et al., 2022. *Exceeding 1.5°C global warming could trigger multiple climate tipping points*. Science, 377(6611). <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abn7950>

Figures:

Fig 1. TIPMIP (Tipping Points Modelling Intercomparison Project), n.d. *What is TIPMIP?* Available at: <https://tipmip.org/about-us-2-0/what-is-tipmip/>

Fig 2. Voosen, P., 2021. *The ocean current that warms Europe may be more resilient than feared*. Science. Available at: <https://www.science.org/content/article/ocean-current-warms-europe-may-be-more-resilient-feared>